

THE ELEMENTS OF DRAMATIZATION IN THE USE OF CREATIVE PRACTICE

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Abstract: this article reveals the main parts of dramatization used as a composition of prose or poetry that is transformed into a performance on stage. In addition, shows the story progresses through interactions between its characters and ends with a message for the audience that are the different elements and affect the quality and thereby the popularity of a play.

Key words: dramatization, composition, plot, elements, poetry, audience, stories, plays, characters, personality

A dramatic work performed on stage is referred to as a dramatization. When a story is dramatized, actors who take on the roles of the characters and act out the story's incidents, moving the plot along, bring the characters and events to life on stage. Actors portray the emotions and personalities of the characters while playing the parts. Through dialogue and nonverbal cues, the plot develops, and audio and visual effects are used to complement the presentation appropriately. The story has a lesson to convey through the characters. It serves as the play's main topic, around which the plot revolves.

While some people view music and visuals as separate components of dramatization, others choose to group them together under staging, which can be thought of as a stand-alone component. Dramatic aspects such as symbolism can be found in the use of lighting, sound effects, costuming, makeup, character gestures and body language, stage design, and props. The main idea of a play is referred to as its theme. Either we can assume it after seeing the full performance, or it can be explicitly communicated through dialogue or action. The philosophical underpinning of the story or a moral lesson that the characters are taught makes up the theme. The audience learns the takeaway from the play.

A play's theme, for instance, can be how power is lost because of improper use of authority or how greed ultimately leads to destruction. A play's topic can be blind love, the power of unselfish love and sacrifice, or genuine friendship. For instance, *Romeo and Juliet* is centered on a violent and overwhelming romantic love between the two characters that drives them to extremes and ultimately results in their self-destruction. The sequence of events in a play determines its plot. The story that the play tells is essentially its plot. The order of events in a play significantly affects how entertaining it is. The relationship between the individuals and the events they are a part of is crucial to the plot. The storyline is made up of the actions, interactions, development of the characters' lives as told by the story, and what ultimately occurs to them. A battle between two people, their relationship, and a struggle within themselves, a conundrum, or any other kind of conflict between a character and himself or another character in the play contributes to the plot of the drama. A series of episodes with a shared cause and effect drive the plot forward. A story typically starts by revealing the past or background of the main character and other characters, as well as the conflict, before moving on to the core topic or climax.

The drama's plot is intertwined with the characters that make up the story. Each character in a play has a distinct personality as well as a set of values and ideologies. The actors must bring the characters in the play to life. The protagonist is the central figure in the play with whom the viewer empathizes. He or she embodies the play's central topic. The antagonist or villain is the one who the protagonist clashes with. While some characters are active throughout the entire narrative, others are merely there to further the plot, while yet others are only seen briefly before or after key scenes and may or may not play a big part.

In a play, dialogues are used to advance the plot. The dialogue between the characters in the play serves as a means of telling the plot to the audience. The impression that the play has on the audiences is significantly influenced by the dialog's content and delivery. The dialogue between characters is how the plot is made clear. They are crucial in illuminating the characters' characteristics. The

words used, the accent, tone, speech pattern, and even the pauses in speaking convey much about the character and aid in illuminating not just his personality but also his social standing, history, and family background as provided by the play. The time and place where a story is set is one of its important parts. The era or time in which the incidents in the play take place, influence the characters in their appearance and personalities. The time setting may affect the central theme of the play, the issues raised, the conflict, and the interactions between the characters. The historical and social context of the play is also defined by the time and place where it is set. The time and the location, in which the story is set, affect the play's staging. Costumes and makeup, the backgrounds and the furniture used, the visuals such as colors and kind of lighting, and the sound are among the important elements of a play that dictate how the story is translated into a stage performance. It is yet another crucial component of dramatization since actor performances have a significant impact on how audiences react to stories.

How well an actor conveys a character's personality and whether his look that including what he wears and how he walks around the stage fits the role he is portraying are key factors in how well an audience will respond to a play. Various performers in various productions of the same play may play the same roles. An actor or actor may be more or less well liked and accepted than another actor playing the same part. As different performers are chosen for various roles, the roles they play are either more or less valued based on how well they perform. The stage performances of a play's characters, particularly those in the key roles, have a direct impact on the play's success and appeal.

References

1. Keith Selby, Robert Giddings, Chris Wensley, *Screening the Novel: The Theory And Practice Of Literary Dramatization* (2016), p. 24.
2. Kathleen J. Turner, *Mass Media and Popular Culture* (1984), p. 32.
3. Grace Evelyn Starks, "Dramatization", *Primary Education*, Volume 22, p. 529.

4. Nancy E. Briggs, Joseph Anthony Wagner, *Children's Literature through Storytelling & Drama* (1979), p. 81.